

19 **Abstract**

20 Biochemistry is an essential yet often undervalued aspect of soil ecology, especially in soil C
21 cycling. We assume based on tradition, intuition or hope that the complexity of biochemistry is confined
22 to the microscopic world, and can be ignored when dealing with whole soil systems. This opinion paper
23 draws attention to patterns caused by basic biochemical processes that permeate the world of
24 ecosystem processes. From these patterns, we can estimate activities of the biochemical reactions of
25 the central C metabolic network and gain insights into the ecophysiology of microbial biosynthesis and
26 growth and maintenance energy requirements; important components of Carbon Use Efficiency (CUE).

27 The biochemical pathways used to metabolize glucose vary from soil to soil, with mostly
28 glycolysis in some soils, and pentose phosphate or Entner-Doudoroff pathways in others. However,
29 notwithstanding this metabolic diversity, glucose use efficiency is high and thus substrate use for
30 maintenance energy and overflow respiration is low in these three soils. These results contradict current
31 dogma based on four decades of research in soil ecology. We identify three main shortcomings in our
32 current understanding of substrate use efficiency: 1) in numeric and conceptual models, we lack
33 appreciation of the strategies that microbes employ to quickly reduce energy needs in response to
34 starvation; 2) production of exudates and microbial turnover affect whole-soil CUE more than variation
35 in maintenance energy demand; and 3) whether tracer experiments can be used to measure the long-
36 term substrate use efficiency of soil microbial communities depends critically on the ability of non-
37 growing cells to take up tracer substrates, how biosynthesis responds to these substrates, as well as on
38 how cellular activities scale to the community level.

39 To move the field of soil ecology forward, future research must consider the details of microbial
40 ecophysiology and develop new tools that enable direct measurement of microbial functioning in intact
41 soils. We submit that ^{13}C metabolic flux analysis is one of those new tools.

42 **Introduction**

43 The topic of this Opinion is ^{13}C metabolic flux analysis and its use for the study of soil microbial
44 ecophysiology, specifically maintenance energy demand, overflow respiration, and substrate use
45 efficiency. We briefly review research on maintenance energy demand in soil communities, followed by
46 an introduction to ^{13}C metabolic flux analysis. We then quantify the process rates of the biochemical
47 pathways within the central C metabolic network using metabolic flux analysis for soil from three
48 distinct ecosystems. These biochemical pathways are important as they release most of the CO_2 ,
49 produce the precursors for biosynthesis, and energy for maintenance and growth. Finally, we address
50 the question whether tracer experiments can be used to measure the overall efficiency of substrate use
51 in soil microbial communities, and identify important knowledge gaps.

52

53 *The Myth of Maintenance*

54 Microbes require energy for cell maintenance and growth. The concepts of cellular energy
55 demand were developed in the middle of the last century (Marr et al. 1963; Payne 1970; Pirt 1965; Roels
56 1980). These early studies found a linear relationship between microbial growth rate and substrate
57 consumption and a positive intercept (Stouthamer and Bettenhausen 1973; Tempest and Neijssel
58 1984). This intercept was interpreted as evidence for a ‘maintenance’ energy cost that was independent
59 of growth rate and did not contribute to biosynthesis (Pirt 1965). Numerous definitions of maintenance
60 have been proposed (see discussion in van Bodegom 2007 and Kempes et al. 2017), but, in this paper,
61 we define maintenance as the processes that require energy, but do not directly contribute to
62 biosynthesis, such as maintenance of solute gradients, motility, and protein and RNA turnover (Pirt
63 1965; Russell and Cook 1995; Schimel and Weintraub 2003; van Bodegom 2007). When growth rates of
64 microbes declined due to resource limitations, proportionally more substrate will be required for
65 maintenance and less will be available for biosynthesis, more substrate-C is released as CO_2 , and Carbon

66 Use Efficiency (CUE, biomass produced per substrate consumed) declines. Researchers during this early
67 period stipulated that maintenance energy demand estimated in chemostat experiments ***referred to***
68 ***growing cells, and suggested that maintenance for non-growing cells was likely lower*** (Pirt 1965).

69 Soil ecologists applied the ideas of microbial energy metabolism and maintenance energy
70 demand to soil ecosystems beginning in the 1970s (Anderson and Domsch 2010). These first studies
71 compared the maintenance energy demand estimated in chemostat experiments with the annual C and
72 energy available in soil ecosystems (Barber and Lynch 1977) and concluded that maintenance energy
73 demand exceeded annual C inputs. For example, Lynch (1982) concluded that “in agricultural and forest
74 soils the energy input may not be enough to satisfy even the maintenance energy requirement”.
75 Similarly, Babiuk and Paul (1970) wrote that “considering the amount of available energy, that the
76 individual cells have enough energy to divide only a few times each year”.

77 Anderson and Domsch, pioneers in soil ecophysiology, determined maintenance energy demand
78 for actively metabolizing (Anderson and Domsch 1985a) and dormant communities (Anderson and
79 Domsch 1985b) using glucose additions. The maintenance demand for actively metabolizing
80 communities was similar to that observed in chemostat experiments, while the maintenance energy
81 requirement estimated for a ‘dormant’ community was two to three orders of magnitude lower. In their
82 studies, Anderson and Domsch assumed that no growth and no death occurred. However, it is now well
83 established that even for soil without substrate amendments, microbial growth and death occur at the
84 same time (Blagodatskaya and Kuzyakov 2013; Cruz-Paredes et al. 2021; Koch et al. 2018; Purcell et al.
85 2021; Reischke et al. 2015).

86 Microbes have an array of strategies to quickly reduce energy consumption when faced with
87 starvation (Greening et al. 2019; Hoehler and Jorgensen 2013; Lever et al. 2015; Lloyd 2021). These
88 strategies include dormancy and quiescence (LaRowe and Amend 2015; Lennon and Jones 2011;
89 Rittershaus et al. 2013), or massive cell death in response to starvation that allow a few cells to feed on

90 their less-fortunate siblings (Aouizerat et al. 2019; Finkel 2006; Jöers et al. 2020). When faced with
91 starvation in laboratory experiments, microbes do not enter a state of perpetual maintenance, but
92 instead actively transition, often within a few hours, to a different physiological state. Starvation is
93 accompanied by a reduction of cell size, reorganization of cellular membranes, increased C reserves, cell
94 wall modifications, and reduced protein and RNA content (Lennon and Jones 2011; Navarro Llorens et
95 al. 2010; Mason-Jones et al. 2021). These survival strategies likely strongly affect soil maintenance
96 energy demand.

97 Price and Sowers (2004) estimated that the maintenance energy cost for a non-growing cell was
98 three orders of magnitude lower for growing cells, while a dormant cell exhibited activity three orders of
99 magnitude lower again. This means that one actively growing cell equaled the activity of 1,000 starved
100 cells and 1,000,000 dormant cells. According to Blagodatskaya and Kuzyakov (2013), about 50% of
101 microbial cells in soil are dormant, 40-49% are non-growing but metabolically active, and 1-10% are
102 actively growing. Using these numbers, one can easily calculate that most community respiration is
103 associated with actively growing cells and less than 5% of respiration comes from dormant or
104 potentially-active cells. These estimates suggest that respiration in soil communities overwhelmingly
105 represents the small minority of growing cells, not the silent majority of non-growing organisms. As a
106 result, we conclude that maintenance energy demand at the level of soil communities is low.

107

108 *To Measure Maintenance*

109 Carbon Use Efficiency is very important for soil organic matter production and C cycling (Allison
110 2014; Cotrufo et al. 2013; Geyer et al. 2016; Hagerty et al. 2018; Manzoni et al. 2018; Schimel and
111 Schaeffer 2012). The concept of CUE – the proportion of substrate-C that is used to make microbial
112 biomass – is straightforward, but surprisingly difficult to measure in soil. Variation in maintenance
113 energy demand affects CUE, suggesting that the measurement of CUE is a good way to estimate

114 maintenance energy demand. However, we now know that the measurement of CUE, for example by
115 measuring the retention of ^{13}C -labeled tracers in microbial biomass, captures multiple processes,
116 including metabolic inefficiencies and C-loss via exudation and microbial turnover (Geyer et al. 2016;
117 Hagerty et al. 2014, 2018; Manzoni et al. 2018). The relative impact of these processes on CUE depends
118 on the method used and the duration of the experiment (Geyer et al. 2016; Hagerty et al. 2014). We
119 submit that it is unproductive to continue with the current tradition of calculating average CUE values
120 without making an effort to untangle the underlying processes of metabolic efficiency, exudation and
121 microbial turnover.

122 In this opinion, we focus on the processes of respiration and biosynthesis only. Variability in
123 maintenance energy demand will directly affect the partitioning of substrate-C over CO_2 and
124 biosynthesis, but not affect the processes of exudation and turnover that also affect CUE. Therefore, we
125 introduce a new term, Biochemical Efficiency or BE, to characterize the C use efficiency of the
126 biochemical processes (Table 1). We also limit ourselves to experiments using ^{13}C labeled glucose and
127 thus to glucose use efficiency. This limitation is justified as much of our conceptual understanding of
128 microbial energy metabolism and CUE is based on glucose-addition experiments. Extrapolating this
129 discussion to other organic compounds is straightforward but goes beyond the goal of this Opinion.

130 If maintenance energy demand is high, more CO_2 will be released by the reactions of the central
131 C metabolic network (glycolysis, TCA cycle, etc.; Fig. 1). More CO_2 will also be released if the energy cost
132 for biosynthesis or membrane transport processes increases (Du et al. 2018; Stouthamer 1973), or if
133 high C availability causes inefficiencies in ATP production and overflow respiration (Manzoni et al. 2012).
134 The value of BE must be measured over a short period of time to minimize the effects of metabolite
135 recycling and turnover. It has been suggested that early response to a glucose addition is mostly limited
136 to the accumulation of C reserves, and thus is not representative of real growth (Sinsabaugh et al. 2013).
137 However, a direct test of this hypothesis using ^{13}C metabolic flux analysis found no evidence for reserve

138 production (Dijkstra et al. 2015). Recent papers by Mason-Jones et al. (2019, 2021) and Manzoni et al.
139 (2021) further detail storage compound formation in soil microbes and its effects on CUE and overflow
140 respiration.

141

142 *¹³C Metabolic Flux Analysis*

143 ¹³C-Based Metabolic Flux Analysis studies the incorporation of ¹³C from position-specific labeled
144 substrates into biosynthesis products (Zamboni et al. 2009). Observed position-specific incorporation is
145 a direct consequence of the flux or activity patterns of central C metabolic network processes. These
146 processes have been studied in depth and appear remarkably similar across all domains of life (Long and
147 Antoniewicz 2019).

148 We adapted the metabolic flux analysis for soil communities using six position-specific ¹³C
149 labeled glucose isotopomers in parallel incubations (Dijkstra et al. 2011a, 2015), but instead of
150 determining ¹³C in biosynthesis products, we measure the ¹³C incorporation into CO₂ for each C atom in
151 the glucose molecule (Dijkstra et al. 2011a,b; Dijkstra et al. 2015; Geyer et al. 2019; Hagerty et al. 2014;
152 van Groenigen et al. 2013). CO₂ is released almost instantaneously after glucose addition, and its isotope
153 composition can be readily measured at low cost using modern laser spectrometers. The position-
154 specific ¹³C-CO₂ measurements usually take about 40 min at room temperature, although can be done
155 within 5 min (A. Martinez, D. Verdi, and P. Dijkstra unpublished results).

156 The proportion of CO₂ production per C atom from position-specific ¹³C-labeled glucose directly
157 reflects the rates of the biochemical processes of the central C metabolic network and BE. Theoretical
158 analysis reveals patterns of position-specific CO₂ production that are associated with high activity of one
159 of the three main metabolic pathways (Fig. 2 left): high CO₂ production from positions C3 and C4 is
160 expected when Embden-Meyerhof-Parnass glycolysis (EMP or 'glycolysis') is highly active, whereas high
161 CO₂ production from position C1 and C4 are predicted when the Pentose Phosphate (PP) or Entner-

162 Doudoroff (ED) pathway activity is dominant. The ED pathway is an evolutionarily ancient glycolytic
163 pathway (Conway 1992; Kopp and Sunna 2020) and is widely distributed among Proteobacteria (Conway
164 1992; Edirisinghe et al. 2016; Kopp and Sunna 2020), but also found in Archaea, diatoms and plants
165 (Chen et al. 2016). The differences in position-specific CO₂ production between a soil community with
166 high PP or a high ED pathway activity are more subtle; high ED activity results in a slightly higher CO₂
167 production from position C2 than C3, while high PP activity produces slightly less CO₂ from C2 than C3.

168 The differences in CO₂ production from different C positions are larger when BE is high (Fig. 3;
169 Dijkstra et al. 2015), because some C atoms are preferentially released as CO₂, while others are
170 incorporated into biosynthesis products. However, as maintenance energy demand increases and BE
171 decreases, CO₂ production per C position becomes more similar. At BE=0, expected for non-growing cells
172 using substrate only to satisfy maintenance energy demand, all glucose-C is released as CO₂ and
173 position-specific CO₂ production is 16.7% (=1/6) of the total CO₂ production (Fig. 3). Therefore, when
174 differences between C-positions are large, we can conclude that BE is high, and thus maintenance or
175 overflow respiration are low.

176

177 *A Modicum of Metabolisms and High Efficiency*

178 Metabolic flux measurements of soil indicated a large proportion of CO₂ from the first C-atom in
179 glucose (C1). We have interpreted this as an indication of a high PP activity (Dijkstra et al. 2011a,b;
180 Dijkstra et al. 2015; Geyer et al. 2019; Hagerty et al. 2014; van Groenigen et al. 2013), but did not
181 consider the effect of an ED pathway (Fig. 1). However, the observed patterns of CO₂ production per C-
182 atom for three distinct soil ecosystems suggested a greater diversity in glucose metabolism than initially
183 proposed (Fig. 2 right). We expanded our metabolic model (Dijkstra et al. 2011a, 2015) to include
184 reactions of the ED pathway and explored whether differences in position-specific CO₂ production (Fig. 2
185 right) were associated with significant differences in glycolysis, PP, or ED pathway activity. Three

186 reactions determined what pathway was used when processing glucose: reaction r2 (glucose
187 metabolized via EMP glycolysis), r10 (PP pathway), and r13 (ED pathway; Fig. 1). Reactions rates
188 exhibited significant differences (Fig. 4 top), with high activity of r2 for the tidal freshwater marsh soil,
189 high activity of r10 for the low elevation cool desert grassland soil, and high activity of r10 and r13 for
190 the high elevation mixed conifer soil. This indicated that glucose was mostly processed via EMP
191 glycolysis in the freshwater marsh soil, via ED and PP pathways in the high elevation mixed conifer soil,
192 and via PP with some contributions from glycolysis and ED pathway for the low elevation desert
193 grassland soil (Fig. 4 middle).

194 Why soil communities utilize different metabolic pathways to catabolize the same substrate is
195 unknown. Further research is needed to determine the geographic distribution of these patterns, and
196 test whether these patterns are the result of genetic differences in community composition (Edirisinghi
197 et al. 2016) or a physiological change in response to soil or environmental conditions (Bore et al. 2017;
198 Thomas et al. 2019). Klingner et al. (2015) analyzed 25 strains of marine bacteria and found that most
199 utilized the ED pathway, concluding that the ED pathway was important in marine ecosystems. It
200 appears from our results that this holds for some soils as well. The ED pathway may provide advantages
201 over the EMP glycolysis because of lower protein cost, and more favorable thermodynamic
202 characteristics, thus compensating for the slightly lower ATP yield under aerobic conditions (Conway
203 1992; Flamholz et al. 2013; Klingner et al. 2015). The ED (and PP) pathways also produce large quantities
204 of NADPH, thus offering protection against oxidative damage (Dijkstra et al. 2011b; Klingner et al. 2015),
205 potentially a crucial requirement in oxygen-rich soil environments.

206 High (EMP) glycolysis activity was also observed in a paddy soil and lake sediment (Krumböck
207 and Conrad 1991), and may be characteristic of anoxic environments. Likewise, glycolysis was the
208 dominant pathway for glucose metabolism in a hot spring at 60°C, but not at higher temperatures (up to
209 90°C; Thomas et al. 2019). Under anoxic conditions, assuming fermentation only, the higher ATP yield of

210 glycolysis over ED pathway may be critical, while the production of NADPH to fight oxidative stress is
211 less important. It should be noted that measurement of CO₂ production per C atom as described here
212 can be supplemented with analysis of position-specific isotope incorporation into biosynthesis products,
213 for example phospholipid fatty acids, thus revealing additional details of soil C metabolism (Apostel et al.
214 2015; Dippold et al. 2019; Wu et al. 2020).

215 Biochemical Efficiency was high in all three soils, although the tidal freshwater marsh soil had a
216 slightly but significantly lower BE (Fig. 4 bottom). BE was high even at high glucose concentrations (2 mg
217 glucose C g⁻¹ soil; Geyer et al. 2019), suggesting inefficiencies associated with overflow respiration were
218 minimal. We conclude that, although soil communities process glucose through different biochemical
219 pathways, glucose is metabolized with high efficiency, and therefore a high maintenance energy
220 demand or overflow respiration can be excluded. Of course, exudation, especially under anoxic or high C
221 conditions, may result in a low Biomass Yield, while changes in microbial turnover will affect apparent
222 CUE (CUE_A).

223

224 *The Full Maintenance?*

225 It has been argued that tracer experiments do not capture the full maintenance demand in soil
226 ecosystems, but only energy demand during a short period that is dominated by active growth
227 immediately after tracer addition (Sinsabaugh et al. 2013, Hagerty et al. 2018). Carbon cycle model
228 calculations suggest that, even if the BE measured shortly after adding an isotope enriched substrate is
229 high, the efficiency across the cell's lifecycle, including an extended period as starved, non-growing cells,
230 is much lower (0.32; Hagerty et al. 2018). However, no clear mechanism was proposed that would
231 prevent us from measuring glucose metabolism from growing and non-growing cells all at once using ¹³C
232 labeled tracers.

233 Models are, by necessity, a simplified or conceptualized representation of reality, and rarely
234 consider the dynamics and speed of microbial responses to substrate limitation and the large
235 differences in maintenance energy requirement between growing and non-growing cells. Instead,
236 models often assume a perpetual state of maintenance and low activity. Although such a state of low
237 activity is possible (with difficulty) in well-mixed chemostat and retentostat experiments (Bisschops et
238 al. 2017), it is unlikely that such activity can be maintained in soil where substrates are strongly localized
239 and depletion zones quick to develop. Moreover, the large reduction in energy demand of non-growing
240 cells (Price and Sowers 2004) comprises only a small fraction of whole-community activity (see above).
241 Additionally, the initial burst of cell growth after glucose addition is rapidly followed by a secondary
242 surge of activity by microbial predators or grazers (e.g., Hungate et al. 2021), thereby reducing the
243 number of non-growing cells with high maintenance cost and maintaining a high community BE.

244 One way to test the hypothesis of temporally separated growth and maintenance after a tracer
245 addition is to add a large pulse of unlabeled tracer, followed by small tracer additions to probe BE using
246 ¹³C metabolic flux analysis across this feast-famine event. In fact, such an experiment, conducted by
247 Geyer et al. (2019), showed that BE was maintained for at least 72-h after a large glucose addition. This
248 again suggests that a glucose addition, even across a growth pulse, does not result in a community with
249 high maintenance energy demands.

250 However, it is possible that tracer compounds (for example glucose) are metabolized by growing
251 but not by non-growing cells. This could occur if glucose instantaneously stimulates a physiological
252 transition from non-growing to growing cells, or if non-growing cells do not have the transporters and
253 metabolic capabilities to utilize extracellular substrates. Added substrate is thought to stimulate growth,
254 an artefact often assigned to tracer experiments (e.g., Sinsabaugh et al 2013). However, such a near
255 instantaneous transition from non-growing to growing contradicts the idea of a lag-phase after glucose
256 addition (Anderson and Domsch 1985a; Blagodatskaya et al. 2007, 2014; Reischke et al. 2015). However,

257 it is possible that an increase in biosynthesis may precede cell replication by several hours. A rapid
258 change in physiology after a glucose addition also undermines the estimates of maintenance energy
259 demand based on work by Anderson and Domsch (1985a,b; 2010). At present, experimental evidence
260 for or against a rapid stimulation of microbial growth in response to glucose is lacking. Similarly, it seems
261 likely that dormant spores do not utilize external substrates, as they are inactive with hardly any ATP
262 and enzyme activities (Keijser et al. 2007; Setlow 2008). This may be true for other survival strategies as
263 well. Results from laboratory studies suggest that large reductions in uptake capacity occur in response
264 to starvation (Casey and Follows 2020; Chubukov and Sauer 2014; Ferenci 2001; Löffler et al. 2017;
265 Navarro Llorens et al. 2010). However dynamics of glucose transport capabilities await experimental
266 verification under *in situ* soil conditions. Such experimental evidence may be obtained using
267 metatranscriptomes or metaproteomes (Chuckran et al. 2020). We submit that it is to the benefit of C
268 cycling models when the underlying mechanisms are experimentally verified.

269 In conclusion, ¹³C metabolic flux analysis shows that BE is high under conditions where we
270 expect low efficiencies associated with high maintenance energy demand or overflow respiration. This
271 appears to be broadly true across soils that utilize different biochemical pathways to process glucose.
272 These results contradict four decades of discussions in soil ecology on the importance of maintenance
273 energy demand in soil communities, and instead point to other factors, such as exudation and microbial
274 turnover, as the cause for variation in CUE. These results require that soil C cycling models incorporate a
275 greater spectrum of microbial traits, including growth and survival strategies, and cell death through
276 predation and grazing. Some of this rethinking of model mechanisms is already happening (e.g., Hagerty
277 et al. 2018; Mason-Jones et al. 2021; Manzoni et al. 2021). New tools, including ¹³C metabolic flux
278 analysis, will need to play an important role to verify that mechanisms hypothesized in models are
279 supported by experimental evidence.

280 ***Acknowledgements***

281 Contributions from authors were made possible by funding from the following agencies: PD and AM:
282 USDA National Institute of Food and Agriculture Foundational Program [award #2017-67019-26396]; PD,
283 AM, and PM: the DOE Terrestrial Ecosystem Science Program [award #DE-SC0014413]; BAH: US
284 Department of Energy's Biological Systems Science Division Program in Genomic Science DE-
285 SCSC0020172; WW: the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the
286 Marie Sklodowska-Curie grant No 840240 and the National Natural Science Foundation of China
287 (42106046); and MD "EcoEnergeticS" DFG DI 2136/17-1.

288 References

- 289 Allison SD (2014) Modeling adaptation of carbon use efficiency in microbial communities. *Front Microbiol*
290 5: 571. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2014.00571>.
- 291 Anderson TH, Domsch KH (1985a) Maintenance carbon requirements of actively-metabolizing microbial
292 populations under *in situ* conditions. *Soil Biol Biochem* 17: 197-203.
293 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717\(85\)90115-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(85)90115-4).
- 294 Anderson TH, Domsch KH (1985b) Determination of ecophysiological maintenance carbon requirements
295 of soil microorganisms in a dormant state. *Biology and Fertility of Soils* 1: 81-89. <https://doi.org/>
- 296 Anderson T-H, Domsch KH (2010) Soil microbial biomass: The eco-physiological approach. *Soil Biology &*
297 *Biochemistry* 42: 2039-2043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2010.06.026>.
- 298 Aouizerat T, Gelman D, Szitenberg A, Gutman I, Glazer S, Reich E, Schoemann M, Kaplan R, Saragovi A,
299 Hazan R, Klutstein M (2019) Eukaryotic adaptation to years-long starvation resembles that of
300 bacteria. *iScience* 19: 545-558. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2019.08.002>.
- 301 Apostel C, Dippold M, Kuzyakov Y (2015) Biochemistry of hexose and pentose transformations in soil
302 analyzed by position-specific labeling and ¹³C-PLFA. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 80: 199-208.
303 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2014.09.005>.
- 304 Babiuk LA, Paul EA (1970) The use of fluorescein isothiocyanate in the determination of the bacterial
305 biomass of grassland soil. *Canadian Journal of Microbiology* 16: 57-62.
306 <https://doi.org/10.1139/m70-011>.
- 307 Barber DA, Lynch JM (1977) Microbial growth in rhizosphere. *Soil Biol Biochem* 9: 305-308.
308 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717\(77\)90001-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(77)90001-3).
- 309 Bisschops MMM, Luttik MAH, Doerr A, Verheijen PJT, Bruggeman F, Pronk JT, Daran-Lapujade P (2017)
310 Extreme calorie restriction in yeast retentostats induces uniform non-quiescent growth arrest.

311 Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Molecular Cell Research 1864: 231-242. doi:
312 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamcr.2016.11.002>.

313 Blagodatskaya E, Blagodatsky S, Anderson TH, Kuzyakov Y (2014) Microbial growth and carbon use
314 efficiency in the rhizosphere and root-free soil. PLoS One 9: e93282. [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0093282)
315 [10.1371/journal.pone.0093282](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0093282).

316 Blagodatskaya E, Kuzyakov Y (2013) Active microorganisms in soil: Critical review of estimation criteria
317 and approaches. Soil Biology & Biochemistry 67: 192-211. [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2013.08.024)
318 [10.1016/j.soilbio.2013.08.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2013.08.024).

319 Blagodatskaya EV, Blagodatsky SA, Anderson TH, Kuzyakov Y (2007) Priming effects in Chernozem induced
320 by glucose and N in relation to microbial growth strategies. Applied Soil Ecology 37: 95-105.
321 [https://doi.org /10.1016/j.apsoil.2007.05.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2007.05.002).

322 Bore EK, Apostel C, Halicki S, Kuzyakov Y, Dippold MA (2017) Microbial metabolism in soil at subzero
323 temperatures: Adaptation mechanisms revealed by position-specific ¹³C labeling. Frontiers in
324 Microbiology 8. [https://doi.org /10.3389/fmicb.2017.00946](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00946).

325 Casey JR, Follows MJ (2020) A steady-state model of microbial acclimation to substrate limitation. PLOS
326 Computational Biology 16: e1008140. [https://doi.org /10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008140](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008140).

327 Chen X, Schreiber K, Appel J, Makowka A, Fährnich B, Roettger M, Hajirezaei MR, Sönnichsen FD, Schönheit
328 P, Martin WF, Gutekunst K (2016) The Entner–Doudoroff pathway is an overlooked glycolytic
329 route in cyanobacteria and plants. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences 113: 5441-
330 5446. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1521916113>.

331 Chubukov V, Sauer U, Spormann AM (2014) Environmental dependence of stationary-phase metabolism
332 in *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*. Applied and Environmental Microbiology 80: 2901-2909.
333 [https://doi.org /10.1128/AEM.00061-14](https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00061-14).

334 Chuckran PF, Fofanov V, Hungate BA, Morrissey EM, Schwartz E, Walkup J, Dijkstra P (2021) Rapid
335 response of nitrogen cycling gene transcription to labile carbon amendments in a soil microbial
336 community. *mSystems* 6. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mSystems.00161-21>.

337 Conway T (1992) The Entner-Doudoroff pathway: history, physiology and molecular biology. *FEMS*
338 *Microbiology Reviews* 9: 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6968.1992.tb05822.x>.

339 Cotrufo MF, Wallenstein MD, Boot CM, Deneff K, Paul E (2013) The Microbial Efficiency-Matrix Stabilization
340 (MEMS) framework integrates plant litter decomposition with soil organic matter stabilization:
341 Do labile plant inputs form stable soil organic matter? *Glob Chang Biol* 19: 988-995.
342 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12113>.

343 Cruz-Paredes C, Tájmel D, Rousk J (2021) Can moisture affect temperature dependences of microbial
344 growth and respiration? *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 156: 108223.
345 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2021.108223>.

346 Dijkstra P, Dalder JJ, Selmants PC, Hart SC, Koch GW, Schwartz E, Hungate BA (2011a) Modeling soil
347 metabolic processes using isotopologue pairs of position-specific ¹³C-labeled glucose and
348 pyruvate. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 43: 1848-1857.
349 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2011.05.001>.

350 Dijkstra P, Ishizu A, Doucett R, Hart SC, Schwartz E, Menyailo OV, Hungate BA (2006) ¹³C and ¹⁵N natural
351 abundance of the soil microbial biomass. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 38: 3257-3266.
352 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2006.04.005>.

353 Dijkstra P, Salpas E, Fairbanks D, Miller EB, Hagerty SB, van Groenigen KJ, Hungate BA, Marks JC, Koch GW,
354 Schwartz E (2015) High carbon use efficiency in soil microbial communities is related to balanced
355 growth, not storage compound synthesis. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 89: 35-43.
356 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2015.06.021>.

357 Dijkstra P, Thomas SC, Heinrich PL, Koch GW, Schwartz E, Hungate BA (2011b) Effect of temperature on
358 metabolic activity of intact microbial communities: Evidence for altered metabolic pathway
359 activity but not for increased maintenance respiration and reduced carbon use efficiency. *Soil
360 Biology & Biochemistry* 43: 2023-2031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2011.05.018>.

361 Dippold MA, Gunina A, Apostel C, Boesel S, Glaser B, Kuzyakov Y (2019) Metabolic tracing unravels
362 pathways of fungal and bacterial amino sugar formation in soil. *European Journal of Soil Science*
363 70: 421-430. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12736>.

364 Du B, Zielinski DC, Monk JM, Palsson BO (2018) Thermodynamic favorability and pathway yield as
365 evolutionary tradeoffs in biosynthetic pathway choice. *Proceedings of the National Academy of
366 Sciences* 115: 11339. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1805367115>.

367 Edirisinghe JN, Weisenhorn P, Conrad N, Xia F, Overbeek R, Stevens RL, Henry CS (2016) Modeling central
368 metabolism and energy biosynthesis across microbial life. *BMC Genomics* 17: 568.
369 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-016-2887-8>.

370 Ferenci T (2001) Hungry bacteria - definition and properties of a nutritional state. *Environ Microbiol* 3:
371 605-611. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1462-2920.2001.00238.x>.

372 Finkel SE (2006) Long-term survival during stationary phase: Evolution and the GASP phenotype. *Nat Rev
373 Microbiol* 4: 113-120. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro1340>.

374 Flamholz A, Noor E, Bar-Even A, Liebermeister W, Milo R (2013) Glycolytic strategy as a tradeoff between
375 energy yield and protein cost. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 110: 10039-10044.
376 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1215283110>.

377 Geyer KM, Dijkstra P, Sinsabaugh R, Frey SD (2019) Clarifying the interpretation of carbon use efficiency
378 in soil through methods comparison. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 128: 79-88.
379 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2018.09.036>.

380 Geyer KM, Kyker-Snowman E, Grandy AS, Frey SD (2016) Microbial carbon use efficiency: accounting for
381 population, community, and ecosystem-scale controls over the fate of metabolized organic
382 matter. *Biogeochemistry* 127: 173-188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-016-0191-y>.

383 Greening C, Grinter R, Chiri E (2019) Uncovering the metabolic strategies of the dormant microbial
384 majority: Towards integrative approaches. *mSystems* 4: e00107-00119.
385 <https://doi.org/10.1128/mSystems.00107-19>.

386 Hagerty SB, Allison SD, Schimel JP (2018) Evaluating soil microbial carbon use efficiency explicitly as a
387 function of cellular processes: Implications for measurements and models. *Biogeochemistry* 140:
388 269-283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-018-0489-z>.

389 Hagerty SB, van Groenigen KJ, Allison SD, Hungate BA, Schwartz E, Koch GW, Kolka RK, Dijkstra P (2014)
390 Accelerated microbial turnover but constant growth efficiency with warming in soil. *Nature*
391 *Climate Change* 4: 903-906. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2361>.

392 Hoehler TM, Jorgensen BB (2013) Microbial life under extreme energy limitation. *Nature Reviews in*
393 *Microbiology* 11: 83-94. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro2939>.

394 Hungate BA, Marks JC, Power ME, Schwartz E, Groenigen KJv, Blazewicz SJ, Chuckran P, Dijkstra P, Finley
395 BK, Firestone MK, Foley M, Greenlon A, Hayer M, Hofmockel KS, Koch BJ, Mack MC, Mau RL, Miller
396 SN, Morrissey EM, Propster JR, Purcell AM, Sieradzki E, Starr EP, Stone BWG, Terrer C, Pett-Ridge
397 J, Lemon KP (2021) The functional significance of bacterial predators. *mBio* 12: e00466-00421.
398 <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00466-21>.

399 Jöers A, Liske E, Tenson T (2020) Dividing subpopulation of *Escherichia coli* in stationary phase. *Research*
400 *in Microbiology* 171: 153-157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2020.02.002>.

401 Keijser BJB, Ter Beek A, Rauwerda H, Schuren F, Montijn R, van der Spek H, Brul S (2007) Analysis of
402 temporal gene expression during bacillus subtilis spore germination and outgrowth. *Journal of*
403 *Bacteriology* 189: 3624-3634. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.01736-06>.

404 Kempes CP, van Bodegom PM, Wolpert D, Libby E, Amend J, Hoehler T (2017) Drivers of bacterial
405 maintenance and minimal energy requirements. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 8. [https://doi.org](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00031)
406 [/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00031](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00031).

407 Klingner A, Bartsch A, Dogs M, Wagner-Döbler I, Jahn D, Simon M, Brinkhoff T, Becker J, Wittmann C (2015)
408 Large-scale ¹³C flux profiling reveals conservation of the Entner-Doudoroff pathway as a glycolytic
409 strategy among marine bacteria that use glucose. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 81:
410 2408-2422. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.03157-14>.

411 Koch BJ, McHugh TA, Hayer M, Schwartz E, Blazewicz SJ, Dijkstra P, van Gestel N, Marks JC, Mau RL,
412 Morrissey EM, Pett-Ridge J, Hungate BA (2018) Estimating taxon-specific population dynamics in
413 diverse microbial communities. *Ecosphere* 9: e02090. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.2090>.

414 Kopp D, Sunna A (2020) Alternative carbohydrate pathways – enzymes, functions and engineering. *Critical*
415 *Reviews in Biotechnology* 40: 895-912. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07388551.2020.1785386>.

416 Krumböck M, Conrad R (1991) Metabolism of position-labelled glucose in anoxic methanogenic paddy soil
417 and lake sediment. *FEMS Microbiology Letters* 85: 247-256. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6968.1991.tb04731.x)
418 [6968.1991.tb04731.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6968.1991.tb04731.x)

419 LaRowe DE, Amend JP (2015) Power limits for microbial life. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 6. [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2015.00718)
420 [10.3389/fmicb.2015.00718](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2015.00718).

421 Lennon JT, Jones SE (2011) Microbial seed banks: The ecological and evolutionary implications of
422 dormancy. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 9: 119-130. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro2504>.

423 Lever MA, Rogers KL, Lloyd KG, Overmann J, Schink B, Thauer RK, Hoehler TM, Jorgensen BB (2015) Life
424 under extreme energy limitation: A synthesis of laboratory- and field-based investigations. *FEMS*
425 *Microbiology Reviews* 39: 688-728. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsre/fuv020>.

426 Lloyd KG (2021) Time as a microbial resource. *Environ Microbiol Rep* 13: 18-21.
427 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-2229.12892>.

428 Löffler M, Simen JD, Müller J, Jäger G, Laghrami S, Schäferhoff K, Freund A, Takors R (2017) Switching
429 between nitrogen and glucose limitation: Unraveling transcriptional dynamics in *Escherichia coli*.
430 Journal of Biotechnology 258: 2-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2017.04.011>.

431 Long CP, Antoniewicz MR (2019) High-resolution ¹³C metabolic flux analysis. Nature Protocols 14: 2856-
432 2877. doi: 10.1038/s41596-019-0204-0.

433 Lynch JM (1982) Limits to microbial growth in soil. J Gen Microbiol 128: 405-410.
434 <https://doi.org/10.1099/00221287-128-2-405>.

435 Manzoni S, Čapek P, Porada P, Thurner M, Winterdahl M, Beer C, Brüchert V, Frouz J, Herrmann AM,
436 Lindahl BD, Lyon SW, Šantrůčková H, Vico G, Way D (2018) Reviews and syntheses: Carbon use
437 efficiency from organisms to ecosystems – definitions, theories, and empirical evidence.
438 Biogeosciences 15: 5929-5949. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-15-5929-2018>.

439 Manzoni S, Ding Y, Warren C, Banfield CC, Dippold MA, Mason-Jones K (2021) Intracellular storage reduces
440 stoichiometric imbalances in soil microbial biomass – A theoretical exploration. Frontiers in
441 Ecology and Evolution 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.714134>.

442 Manzoni S, Taylor P, Richter A, Porporato A, Agren GI (2012) Environmental and stoichiometric controls
443 on microbial carbon-use efficiency in soils. New Phytologist 196: 79-91.
444 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2012.04225.x>.

445 Marr AG, Clark DJ, Nilson EH (1963) Maintenance requirement of *Escherichia coli*. Ann NY Acad Sci 102:
446 536-548. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.1963.tb13659.x>.

447 Mason-Jones K, Robinson SL, Veen GF, Manzoni S, van der Putten WH (2021) Microbial storage and its
448 implications for soil ecology. The ISME Journal. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-021-01110-w>.

449 Mason-Jones K, Banfield CC, Dippold MA (2019) Compound-specific ¹³C stable isotope probing confirms
450 synthesis of polyhydroxybutyrate by soil bacteria. Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry
451 33: 795-802. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.8407>.

452 Navarro Llorens JM, Tormo A, Martinez-Garcia E (2010) Stationary phase in Gram-negative bacteria. FEMS
453 Microbiol Rev 34: 476-495. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6976.2010.00213.x>.

454 Payne WJ (1970) Energy yields and growth of heterotrophs. Annu Rev Microbiol 24: 17-52.
455 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.mi.24.100170.000313>.

456 Pirt SJ (1965) The maintenance energy of bacteria in growing cultures. Proceedings of the Royal Society
457 Series B-Biological Sciences 163: 224-231. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.1965.0069>.

458 Price PB, Sowers T (2004) Temperature dependence of metabolic rates for microbial growth,
459 maintenance, and survival. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A 101: 4631-4636.
460 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0400522101>.

461 Purcell AM, Hayer M, Koch BJ, Mau RL, Blazewicz SJ, Dijkstra P, Mack MC, Marks JC, Morrissey EM, Pett-
462 Ridge J, Rubin RL, Schwartz E, van Gestel NC, Hungate BA (2021) Decreased growth of wild soil
463 microbes after 15 years of transplant-induced warming in a montane meadow. Global Change
464 Biology. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15911>.

465 Reischke S, Kumar MGK, Bååth E (2015) Threshold concentration of glucose for bacterial growth in soil.
466 Soil Biology & Biochemistry 80: 218-223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2014.10.012>.

467 Rittershaus ES, Baek SH, Sassetti CM (2013) The normalcy of dormancy: Common themes in microbial
468 quiescence. Cell Host Microbe 13: 643-651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2013.05.012>.

469 Roels JA (1980) Application of macroscopic principles to microbial metabolism. Biotechnol Bioeng 22:
470 2457-2514. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.260221202>.

471 Russell JB, Cook GM (1995) Energetics of bacterial growth: Balance of anabolic and catabolic reactions.
472 Microbiol Rev 59: 48-62.

473 Schimel JP, Schaeffer SM (2012) Microbial control over carbon cycling in soil. Front Microbiol 3: 348.
474 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2012.00348>.

475 Schimel JP, Weintraub MN (2003) The implications of exoenzyme activity on microbial carbon and
476 nitrogen limitation in soil: A theoretical model. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 35: 549-563.
477 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(03\)00015-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(03)00015-4).

478 Setlow P (2008) Dormant spores receive an unexpected wake-up call. *Cell* 135: 410-412.
479 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2008.10.006>.

480 Sinsabaugh RL, Manzoni S, Moorhead DL, Richter A (2013) Carbon use efficiency of microbial communities:
481 Stoichiometry, methodology and modelling. *Ecology Letters* 16: 930-939.
482 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12113>.

483 Stouthamer AH (1973) A theoretical study on the amount of ATP required for synthesis of microbial cell
484 material. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 39 (1973) 545-565. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02578899>.

485 Stouthamer AH, Bettenhausen C (1973) Utilization of energy for growth and maintenance in continuous
486 and batch cultures of microorganisms - re-evaluation of method for determination of ATP
487 production by measuring molar growth yields. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 301: 53-70.
488 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4173\(73\)90012-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4173(73)90012-8).

489 Tempest DW, Neijssel OM (1984) The status of Y_{ATP} and maintenance energy as biologically interpretable
490 phenomena. *Annu Rev Microbiol* 38: 459-486.
491 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.mi.38.100184.002331>.

492 Thomas SC, Tamadonfar KO, Seymour CO, Lai D, Dodsworth JA, Murugapiran SK, Eloe-Fadros EA, Dijkstra
493 P, Hedlund BP (2019) Position-specific metabolic probing and metagenomics of microbial
494 communities reveal conserved central carbon metabolic network activities at high temperatures.
495 *Frontiers in Microbiology* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.01427>.

496 van Bodegom P (2007) Microbial maintenance: A critical review on its quantification. *Microb Ecol* 53: 513-
497 523. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-006-9049-5>.

498 van Groenigen KJ, Forristal D, Jones M, Smyth N, Schwartz E, Hungate B, Dijkstra P (2013) Using metabolic
499 tracer techniques to assess the impact of tillage and straw management on microbial carbon use
500 efficiency in soil. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 66: 139-145.
501 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2013.07.002>.

502 Wu W, Dijkstra P, Dippold MA (2020) ¹³C analysis of fatty acid fragments by gas chromatography mass
503 spectrometry for metabolic flux analysis. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 284: 92-106.
504 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2020.05.032>.

505 Zamboni N, Fendt S-M, Rühl M, Sauer U (2009) ¹³C-based metabolic flux analysis. *Nature Protocols* 4: 878-
506 892. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2009.58>.

507 Figure Legends

508

509 *Fig. 1. Metabolic model with three glucose metabolizing pathways: Embden-Meyerhof-Parnas (EMP, r2 -*
510 *red arrow) glycolysis, Pentose Phosphate pathway (r10 - blue), and Entner-Doudoroff (ED, r13 - yellow)*
511 *pathway. Pathway reactions (r2 ... r15) and biomass reactions (br1 ... br8) are expressed as moles relative*
512 *to r1 (set at 100 moles). Abbreviations: AcCoA, acetyl-CoA; α KG, α -ketoglutarate; E4P, erythrose-4P; F6P,*
513 *fructose-6P; G3P, glyceraldehyde-3P; G6P, glucose-6P; KDPG, 2-keto-3-deoxy-6-phosphogluconate; OAA,*
514 *oxaloacetate; PYR, pyruvate; RU5P, ribulose-5P; S7P, sedoheptulose-7P. Additional details in Dijkstra et al.*
515 *(2011a).*

516

517 *Fig. 2. Modeled (left) and observed (right) CO₂ production per C-position (means and stdev, n=4).*
518 *Modeled values are CO₂ production per C atom calculated using a metabolic model with EMP, PP, ED*
519 *pathway and TCA cycle reactions (Fig. 1; adapted from Dijkstra et al. 2011a, 2015). Modeled CO₂*
520 *production per C atom are for BE = 0.6 and maximal activity of EMP, PPP, and ED respectively.*
521 *Observations are based on measurement of CO₂ production from 6 glucose mono-isotopomers in parallel*
522 *incubations for soil from the Jug Bay tidal freshwater marsh near Annapolis, Maryland (FM; A. Martinez,*
523 *P. Megonigal, and P. Dijkstra, in prep), a low elevation cool desert grassland (GL) and a high elevation*
524 *meadow in mixed conifer forest (MC) near Flagstaff, Arizona (Dijkstra et al. 2007). Theoretical*
525 *calculations are done for maximum EMP activity by setting r13 at zero, and r10 at the lowest rate that*
526 *satisfies biosynthesis demand (br8), maximum PP activity by setting r13 and r10 to zero, and maximum*
527 *ED activity by setting r2 to zero and PP at lowest value that satisfies br2 plus br8 (Fig. 1).*

528

529 *Fig. 3. Relationship between Biochemical Efficiency (BE) and CO₂ production from C-atom 1 in glucose*
530 *relative to CO₂ production from uniformly-labeled glucose (CU) modeled for a central C metabolic*
531 *network dominated by PP pathway activity. Results from theoretical calculations using metabolic model*
532 *(Fig. 1), r₂ and r₁₃ set at 0, and varying r₁₀ and br₁ to change BE.*

533

534 *Fig. 4. Differences in activity for initial reactions of EMP glycolysis (r₂), PP (r₁₀) and ED (r₁₃) pathways*
535 *(upper panel), proportion of activity of the three main glucose metabolizing pathways (middle), and*
536 *Biochemical Efficiency (lower) of a high elevation meadow in mixed conifer forest (MC), low elevation cold*
537 *desert grassland (GL) and a tidal freshwater marsh (FM). BE is calculated as $\frac{6 \times r_1 - \sum CO_2}{6 \times r_1}$. Means and 95%*
538 *confidence intervals are calculated using 1,000 random samples from the observed distribution of CO₂*
539 *production per C atom (Fig. 2 right) and solving the metabolic model (Fig. 1) using a Generalized Reduced*
540 *Gradient non-linear optimization method with 100 restarts (Solver – Excel; Dijkstra et al. 2011a).*

541

542

543 *Table 1: Terminology and definitions. U = Uptake, R = respiration, EX = exudation, T = microbial turnover.*
 544 *First column contains names of variables used in this paper, with mathematical representation in second*
 545 *column. Last three columns contain corresponding variable names used by Geyer et al., 2016, Hagerty et*
 546 *al. 2018, and Manzoni et al. 2018.*

Variable	Equation	Geyer et al. 2016 [#]	Hagerty et al. 2018 [*]	Manzoni et al. 2018 [§]
Biochemical efficiency (BE)	$(U-R)/U$	CUE _C	CUE _S	CUE
Biomass Yield	$(U-R-EX)/U$	CUE _C = CUE _P	CUE	GGE
Apparent CUE (CUE _A)	$(U-R-EX-T)/U$	CUE _E	CUE _C	CUE _A

547 [#]CUE_C is community-scale CUE; CUE_E is ecosystem-scale CUE (Geyer et al. 2016). ^{*}CUE_S is substrate-based
 548 CUE; CUE_C is concentration-based CUE (Hagerty et al. 2018). [§]GGE is Gross Growth Efficiency; CUE_A is
 549 apparent CUE (Manzoni et al. 2018).

550 Fig. 1

551

552 Fig. 2

553

554 Fig. 3.

555

556 Fig. 4

557